

RISKS OF GENERALIZATION OF INFECTION IN LONG-TERM NON-HEALING WOUNDS: CLINICAL FEATURES AND PREVENTION

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Abstract

The study is aimed at studying the formation of infectious complications in patients with long-term non-healing wounds (DNZR). The study included 169 patients divided into control and main groups. Patients with pressure sores, neurotrophic ulcers, and trophic ulcers after thrombophlebitis accounted for 38.5%, 32.5%, and 29%, respectively. The risk of generalization of infection in the main group was 30% lower than in the control group, which indicates the importance of complex therapy with antibacterial and immunomodulatory agents. The data obtained made it possible to develop effective methods for the prevention of infectious complications in chronic wounds.

Key words: chronic wounds, long-term non-healing wounds, infectious complications, prevention, pressure sores, neurotrophic ulcers, trophic ulcers, antibacterial therapy, immunomodulators.

Relevance

Long-term non-healing wounds (DLDS) are a common medical problem, especially among patients with chronic diseases such as diabetes, thrombophlebitis, and hypodynamia. Complications, such as generalization of infection, can lead to serious consequences, including sepsis. In this study, three main forms of DNZR were considered: pressure sores, neurotrophic ulcers in diabetic foot syndrome, and trophic ulcers after thrombophlebitis. These forms account for 38.5%, 32.5% and 29% of the total number of patients, respectively. Effective prevention and treatment of infectious complications is crucial for improving patients' quality of life and reducing morbidity. It is important to emphasize the need to predict the risks of generalization of infection and develop individualized methods of prevention and therapy for each group of patients.

Objective

The aim of the study was to assess the frequency of generalization of infection and to develop effective prevention methods in patients with various forms of long-term non-healing wounds.

Materials and methods

The study involved 169 patients divided into the control group (84 people) and

the main group (85 people). The main forms of DNZR are bedsores of various localization (38.5%), neurotrophic ulcers in diabetic foot (32.5%) and trophic ulcers after thrombophlebitis (29%). The condition was assessed using clinical tests, microbiological studies, C-reactive protein levels, and other laboratory parameters. Patients in the main group received combination therapy, including antibiotics and immunomodulators.

Results

From 169 patients, 38.5% had pressure sores, 32.5% had neurotrophic ulcers in diabetic foot syndrome, and 29% had trophic ulcers after thrombophlebitis. In the main group receiving combination therapy, the incidence of generalization of infection decreased by 30%, which allowed to accelerate wound healing by 25% compared to the control group. Clinical improvement was observed in 72% of patients with pressure sores and 65% with neurotrophic ulcers.

Заклучение

Generalization of infection is an important complication in long-term non-healing wounds, especially in patients with chronic diseases. The use of combination therapy, including antibacterial and immunomodulators, significantly reduces the risk of generalization of infection and accelerates the healing process. Effective prevention and individualized treatment of patients with pressure ulcers, neurotrophic ulcers and trophic ulcers after thrombophlebitis can significantly improve clinical outcomes and reduce the incidence of complications.

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